

THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION IS THE MAIN RESOURCE
INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT SOCIETY

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Abstract. *To achieve this goal, a general scientific systems approach was applied, which views higher education as a complex, dynamic system. A conceptual (theoretical) analysis of key trends in the development of the modern higher education system was utilized. Contemporary scientific publications served as the theoretical and methodological basis for the study. An analysis of the scientific literature demonstrates that certain theoretical prerequisites for studying higher education issues have emerged. A review of scientific publications suggests that the socioeconomic conditions for the development of higher education significantly influence the innovative development of society. The study identified factors that determine the resource potential of higher education in the innovative development of society.*

Key words: *higher education, innovative development, innovative economy, pedagogical innovations, educational policy, knowledge economy.*

Higher education can become the primary resource for achieving society's stated goals. In terms of scale and impact on all aspects of societal development, it is unparalleled, and therefore must meet the modern demands of social development.

Innovative development, like education, is a socially oriented activity that regulates all other socially significant activities—that is, a meta-activity that shapes modern culture and significantly influences the long-term development and functioning of society.

An analysis of the scientific literature indicates that certain theoretical prerequisites for studying higher education issues have emerged [1,2].

The innovative focus of research is increasingly evident in contemporary publications. The scientific study and substantiation of innovation processes is being pursued very actively. A comprehensive concept of an innovative economy has now emerged in the scientific community, including the higher education system.

In a review article, G.Sessere proposes a concept of the “soft innovation economy”. Soft innovation represents a corresponding additional source of economic development that has received little attention to date, primarily innovation in the service sector and the knowledge economy [3]. The authors highlight key issues, examine some of the new innovations that have emerged in the digital age, and outline a change agenda, calling for long-term thinking to mitigate the negative consequences of an increasingly automated and digital economy. K.Frey points out that innovations are changing the nature of employment in entire industries and spheres of activity, altering the dynamics of economic growth, and changing the labor market [4]. According to T.Schott and V.Jensen, who conducted a study in the field of assessing the impact of institutional environment factors on the level of innovation activity, institutional support does not

directly affect the innovation activity of organizations, but has a positive effect on strengthening the links between them, which, in turn, stimulates organizations to implement innovations [5].

A review of scientific publications suggests that the socioeconomic conditions for the development of higher education have a significant impact on the innovative development of society.

These conditions, in our opinion, include, first and foremost, the formation of an innovative environment for universities, the managerial potential of educational institutions, financial support for university operations, a specific educational environment, innovative approaches to teaching at universities, the professional competencies of faculty, and the success of faculty members.

Changes in the material and technical base of production entail changes in the personal factor of production. This is expressed in its intellectualization.

Knowledge and information occupy a central place in the new society, becoming the primary resources. Information and knowledge can also be embodied in the tangible elements of production – technology and equipment. However, only knowledge and information accumulated by people have the capacity to self-extend and be transformed into a creative process. Their importance overshadows traditional economic resources: capital, labor, and land.

Changed external and internal conditions and the experience of other countries require recognition of the priority of developing education alongside culture, art, science, and high technology, as evidence of the importance of the country's innovative development. It is essential to ensure access to a quality education; to transition from a mass education system to continuous, individualized education for all; and to develop education inextricably linked

with global fundamental science, focused on the development of creative, socially responsible individuals.

Historical experience demonstrates that the content, structure, organization, and functions of the education system do not remain static, but are constantly changing under the influence of external influences. The primary impetus at the stage of modern societal development is the needs of the economy, namely: the education of the workforce is a necessary and important aspect of its reproduction, and, at the same time, of the entire reproduction process as a whole. The existing structure of production, its volume, and technical conditions must be provided with personnel of the appropriate size, industry, and professional qualifications.

The key requirement for motivating university employees is the relevance of the chosen motivational methods for each individual employee. Motivation can be updated through surveys, with a choice of available tangible or intangible forms. Age groups of employees must also be considered, as different generations prefer different motivational programs. In addition to these differences, existing subjective characteristics should be considered: some people are more comfortable working with clear objectives and deadlines, while others, conversely, require autonomy in distributing the workload and an interest in the tasks at hand.

Pedagogical innovations are developed by philosophers, methodologists, and educational leaders, but any innovation will be meaningless if teachers do not perceive interest and benefit from the innovation process. Therefore, the staff motivation system in educational organizations must be flexible and individualized [6].

Work will be effective if teachers understand the results management expects of them and when, are motivated to achieve results, experience satisfaction in their work, and are prepared for changes occurring in the education system. The socio-pedagogical climate within the team is favorable for productive work; the necessary resources and conditions for implementing the tasks set before the teacher are available [7].

The study identified factors that determine the resource potential of higher education in the innovative development of society:

1. A strategy for the accelerated development of the higher education system, providing impetus for economic and social development.
2. Developing a new concept for training personnel capable of effectively managing innovation processes and developing and implementing innovative projects.
3. Providing opportunities for high-quality education, inextricably linked to global fundamental science and focused on developing creative, socially responsible individuals.
4. A system of effective education financing that improves the quality of education, guarantees its accessibility for the population, and provides educational institutions with the necessary quantity and quality of resources.
5. Stimulating the productive work of teachers in the face of a pressing public demand for a faculty that meets the modern demands of society.
6. A flexible and individualized system of staff motivation in educational organizations.
7. Objectivity, transparency, dynamism and flexibility of criteria for assessing the success of university staff [8].

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